

Substituent effect on the infrared and Raman spectra of *N*-(substituted-phenyl)-2,2-dichloroacetamides, $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCHCl_2$ ($X = o/m/p-CH_3$ or Cl; $y = 1, 2$ or 3)

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Several substituted *N*-(phenyl)-2,2-dichloroacetamides of the configuration $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCHCl_2$ (where, X = H, CH₃ or Cl and y = 1, 2 or 3) have been synthesized and their infrared and Raman spectra measured in the solid state with the objective of correlating CO and NH frequencies of these substituted phenyldichloroacetamides with those of substituted phenylchloroacetamides and trichloroacetamides. The study reveals that there is no systematic variation in the frequencies with the substitution. The effect of substitution in the phenyl ring in terms of electron-donating and electron-withdrawing groups could not be generalized. The same trend is observed even with disubstituted phenyl-2,2-dichloroacetamides, which may be due to the varying crystalline states of the amides as the spectra are measured in the solid state. The infrared and Raman frequencies of the amides of the configuration $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOR$ (where, X = H, CH₃ or Cl and y = 1, 2 or 3 and R = CH₂Cl, CHCl₂, CCl₃) have also been examined for comparison purpose. The entire data indicate that neither the infrared CO or NH absorption frequencies nor the Raman scattered CO or NH frequencies show regular trends in all these compounds for the reasons stated above.

Spectroscopic and crystal structural studies give valuable informations on bond properties^{1,2}. Amides are of fundamental chemical interest as conjugation between nitrogen lone-pair electrons and the carbonyl π -bond results in distinct physical and chemical properties³. The amide moiety is an important constituent of many biologically significant compounds. Therefore, an understanding of the formation, properties and reactions of amides is central to future development in such areas as polypeptides and protein chemistry. Many imides, hydroxamic acids and hydrazides exhibit pharmacological activity which has further stimulated recent interest in their chemistry. Further, many acetanilides exhibit fungicidal, herbicidal and pharmacological activities. Thus we are interested in the spectroscopic and X-ray diffraction studies of amides in their crystalline state⁴⁻⁶. We have reported ³⁵Cl NQR spectra of a number of *N*-(chlorophenyl)chloroacetamides of the configuration $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCH_{3-y}Cl_y$ (where, X = CH₃ or Cl and y = 1 or 2)^{4,5}, to see how the -NHCO- bond parameters vary with substitution of the electron-donating and electron-withdrawing groups in the benzene ring and in the side-chain.

Although there are reports on IR and Raman spectra of anilines, amides, *N*-phenylchloroacetamides and *N*-(phenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamide⁷, no reports are available on substituted *N*-(phenyl)-2,2-dichloroacetamides. We report herein

the infrared and Raman spectra of a number of substituted *N*-(phenyl)-2,2-dichloroacetamides, $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCHCl_2$ (where, X = H, CH₃ or Cl and y = 1, 2 or 3).

Results and Discussion

The infrared and Raman frequencies of the compounds measured are shown in Tables 1-4. IR and Raman frequencies of the related compounds from the literature are also included for comparison (Tables 5, 6).

Assignment of various bands in substituted amides in general has been dealt in detail². Hence, the general assignment of frequencies to various modes is not repeated here. The discussion is limited to the effect of substitution in the phenyl ring of the compounds studied and their comparison and correlation with the related compounds (Tables 5, 6 and Figs. 1-4).

N-(Phenyl)-2,2-dichloroacetamide shows very strong C=O absorption frequencies at 1668 cm⁻¹ in the IR and 1680 cm⁻¹ in the Raman (scattered frequency). The frequencies for other substituted phenyldichloroacetamides lie in the ranges 1687-1674 (IR) and 1680-1697 cm⁻¹ (Raman). The N-H broad absorption frequencies for the parent compound, *N*-(phenyl)-2,2-dichloroacetamide are at 3295 cm⁻¹ in the IR and 3118 cm⁻¹ in the Raman, whereas for others

Table 1. IR frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCHCl_2$ with X_y

Assignment	H	2-CH ₃	3-CH ₃	4-CH ₃	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	3,5-(CH ₃) ₂	2,4,6-(CH ₃) ₃
C-Cl str	665m	666m	659m	668m	698m	674m	649m	656s	650m	662m	649m
	685s	705s	686s	730s	779s	698s	693s	708s	695s	681s	675m
									757s	746s	746s
ArC-H def	818m	808m	808m	810m	808m	808m	821m	809m	806m	805m	829m
	850s	833s	834s	838s	843s	843s	852s	857s	816s	845s	841s
		875s		871s	868s	868s	878s	871s		867s	
C-N def	1283s	1279m	1288m	1289m	1274m	1272m	1276m	1284m	1282m	1290m	1248m
AliC-H def	1340m	1338m	1343m	1345m	1339m	1339m	1334m	1338m	1350m	1324m	1334m
ArC=C str	1550m	1524m	1542m	1516m	1518m	1518m	1525m	1516m	1508m	1508m	1527m
	1600m	1559m	1560m	1556m	1571m	1571m	1574m	1572m	1550m	1571m	1542m
C=O str	1668s	1676s	1682s	1674s	1687s	1687s	1681s	1681s	1675s	1677s	1680s
AliCH str	-	2968w	2934w	2920w	2942w	2942w	2977w	2937w	2940w	2933w	2958w
		2978w	2976w	2941w	2950w	2950w	2988w	2965w	2979w	2988w	2989w
					2990w	2990w			2993w		2993w
ArC-H str	3030w	3036w	3030w	3025w	3042w	3042w	3022w	3055w	3044w	3057w	3002w
			3047w	3039w	3058w	3052w	3060w	3078w	3062w	3079w	
N-H str	3295w	3236w	3253w	3211w	3241w	3242w	3242w	3231w	3295w	3261w	3196w

Table 2. IR frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCHCl_2$ with X_y

Assignment	H	2-Cl	3-Cl	4-Cl	2,3-Cl ₂	2,4-Cl ₂	2,5-Cl ₂	2,6-Cl ₂	3,4-Cl ₂	3,5-Cl ₂	2,4,6-Cl ₃
C-Cl str	665m	651s	636s	636s	659m	663m	636m	634m	635m	649m	660m
	685s	755s	667m	740s	742s	753s	675m	674m	667m	673m	756s
			732s				760s	757s	763s	753s	792s
ArC-H def	818m	871m	867m	863m	810m	809m	806m	804m	809m	807m	813m
	850m				848m	843m	874m	881m	879m	867m	822m
											860m
C-N def	1283m	1280m	1280s	1288m	1297m	1274m	1264m	1272m	1283m	1290m	1292m
AliC-H def	1340m	1338m	1334m	1338s	1330m	1328m	1327m	1330m	1330m	1335m	1332m
C=C str	1550m	1542s	1535m	1550s	1518m	1533m	1547m	1549m	1544m	1530m	1534m
	1600m	1592m	1596s		1550m	1574m	1571m	1581m	1568m	1533m	1568m
					1593m		1595m			1581m	
C=O str	1668s	1677s	1693s	1681s	1689s	1689s	1665s	1667s	1682s	1665s	1684s
AliC-H str		2935w	3012w	2954w	2970w	2974w	2978w	2924w	2973w	2998w	2956w
				2992w	2997w	2994w	2991w	2998w	2915w		2994w
ArC-H str	3030w	3058w	3081w	3093m	3059w	3064w	3064w	3029w	3044w	3052w	3048w
N-H str	3295w	3251w	3197w	3278w	3273w	3206w	3241w	3245w	3294w	3268w	3212w

they vary between 3295 and 3241 (IR) and 3056 and 3196 cm^{-1} (Raman) except for *N*-(2,4,6-trimethylphenyl)-2,2-dichloroacetamide, showing N-H frequency at 3196 cm^{-1} (IR and Raman). The C-N deformation frequencies for *N*-(phenyl)-2,2-dichloroacetamide are at 1283 (IR) and 1247 cm^{-1} (Raman) and for others the frequencies are in the ranges 1272–1290 (IR) and 1213–1282 cm^{-1} (Raman). *N*-(Phenyl)-2,2-dichloroacetamide shows two C-Cl absorption frequencies at 665 and 685 (IR) and 568 and 760 cm^{-1} (Raman); for others they are in the ranges 656–757 (IR) and 568–687 cm^{-1} (Raman).

The trends in the variation of C-H and $\bar{C}=\bar{C}$ IR and Raman scattered frequencies also follow almost the same pattern as that of C=O frequencies. As may be seen, there is no systematic variation with substitution. The effect of substitution in the phenyl ring in terms of electron-donating and electron-withdrawing groups could not be generalized. It is also evident from the IR spectra of amides of the configuration, $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOR'$ (where, X = H, CH₃ or Cl; y = 1, 2 or 3; R' = CH₂Cl, CHCl₂ or CCl₃), that the CO and NH frequencies in these compounds also do not show regular trends (Tables 5, 6). The $\nu_{C=O}$ and ν_{N-H} frequencies of

Table 3 Raman frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCHCl_2$ with X_y

Assignment	H	2-CH ₃	3-CH ₃	4-CH ₃	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	3,5-(CH ₃) ₂	2,4,6-(CH ₃) ₃
C-Cl str	568m	590m	572m	573m	568m	571m	569m	573m	574s	530m	581m
	760m		681m	677m	687m	665m	676m	673m	668m		670m
ArC-H def	810m	775m	816s	850m	825m	750m	796m	785m	762m	803s	831m
	875m	810s		882m		820m		824m	815m	827m	850w
		880m				865m			829m		
C-N def	1247m	1225m	1268m	1251m	1270m	1282m	1275m	1275m	1262m	1213m	1254m
AlC-H def	1355s	1350s	1348s	1348s	1346s	1350s	1344m	1351m	1354s	1350s	1347m
C=C str	1568s	1550m	1556m	1506vs	1576m	1557m	1556m	1567m	1566s	1581m	1575m
C=O str	1680m	1675s	1662m	1620s	1611s	1622s	1600m	1615s	1676vs	1680m	1656m
ArC-H str	2900w	3010w	3000w	3018w	2893w	2999w	3008w	2989w	2955w	2905w	2991w
N-H str	3118w	3167w	3158w	3147m	3061m	3056m	3148w	3144w	3153m	3162m	3196w

Table 4 Raman frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCHCl_2$ with X_y

Assignment	H	2-Cl	3-Cl	4-Cl	2,3-Cl ₂	2,4-Cl ₂	2,5-Cl ₂	2,6-Cl ₂	3,4-Cl ₂	3,5-Cl ₂	2,4,6-Cl ₃
C-Cl str	568m	671m	569m	584m	559m	659m	585m	531m	638m	585m	531m
	760m	695m		658m	605m		598s	621m	667m	627m	676m
ArC-H def	810m	779m	790m	880m	790m	885m	770m	806m	809m	820m	803m
	875m	824m			803m		822m	890m	879m	865m	898m
		879m			822m		894m				
		884m									
C-N def	1222m	1225m	1238m	1241m	1226m	1253m	1242m	1267m	1238m	1226m	1241m
AlC-H def	1355s	1346m	1350vs	1350s	1349m	1342m	1343m	1340m	1347m	1345vs	1340m
C=C str	1568s	1551m	1550vs	1570m	1554m	1557m	1601m	1552m	1539m	1558m	1580m
C=O str	1680s	1689s	1667vs	1691m	1694s	1695s	1691s	1641m	1682s	1685s	1697s
ArC-H str	2900m	2886m	2954m	3000m	2922m	2897w	2943m	2904m	2883w	2800m	2980w
N-H str	3121w	3191w	3158w	3134m	3050m	3078m	3187w	3144w	3225m	3268m	3096w

Table 5 Selected infrared frequencies (cm^{-1}) of configuration $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOR$ with X_y and R

X_y	R= CH ₂ Cl		R= CHCl ₂		R= CCl ₃		X_y	R= CH ₂ Cl		R= CHCl ₂		R= CCl ₃	
	ν_{CO}	ν_{NH}	ν_{CO}	ν_{NH}	ν_{CO}	ν_{NH}		ν_{CO}	ν_{NH}	ν_{CO}	ν_{NH}	ν_{CO}	ν_{NH}
H	1680	3280	1668	3295	1695	3310	H	1680	3280	1688	3295	1695	3310
2-CH ₃	1637	3340	1676	3236	1705	3330	2-Cl	1675	3260	1677	3251	1717	3275
3-CH ₃	1668	3365	1682	3253	1695	3290	3-Cl	1682	3275	1693	3197	1698	3253
4-CH ₃	1676	3365	1674	3211	1695	3300	4-Cl	1670	3270	1681	3278	1709	3262
2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	1665	3290	1687	3241	1720	3310	2,3-Cl ₂	1680	3280	1689	3273	1744	3370
2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	1665	3238	1687	3242	1700	3295	2,4-Cl ₂	1675	3250	1689	3206	1715	3325
2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	1680	3268	1681	3242	1700	3305	2,5-Cl ₂	1685	-	1665	3241	1735	3364
2,6-(CH ₃) ₂	1668	3260	1681	3231	1700	3425	2,6-Cl ₂	1685	3210	1667	3245	1705	3270
3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	1678	3300	1675	3295	1700	3270	3,4-Cl ₂	1675	3320	1682	3294	1702	3250
3,5-(CH ₃) ₂	1665	3310	1677	3261	1680	3430	3,5-Cl ₂	1685	3290	1665	3268	1718	3305
2,4,6-(CH ₃) ₃	1665	3200	1680	3196	-	-	2,4,6-Cl ₃	-	-	1684	3212	-	-

both the methyl and chloro substituted phenyl-2,2-dichloroacetamides and those of the other ω -chlorosubstituted acetamides have been correlated (Figs. 1-4).

Experimental

The substituted *N*-phenyldichloroacetamides were prepared from substituted aniline, dichloroacetic acid and phos-

Table 6. Selected Raman frequencies (cm^{-1}) of configuration $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOR$ with X_y and R

X_y	R=	CH_2Cl		$CHCl_2$		CCl_3		X_y	R=	CH_2Cl		$CHCl_2$		CCl_3	
		γ_{CO}	γ_{NH}	γ_{CO}	γ_{NH}	γ_{CO}	γ_{NH}			γ_{CO}	γ_{NH}	γ_{CO}	γ_{NH}	γ_{CO}	γ_{NH}
H		1691	3055	1680	3118	1700	3325	H		1691	3055	1680	3118	1700	3325
2- CH_3		1662	3190	1675	3167	1700	2979	2-Cl		1675	3080	1689	3191	1705	-
3- CH_3		1673	2968	1662	3158	1690	3286	3-Cl		1680	3069	1667	3158	1600	-
4- CH_3		1670	2955	1620	3147	1690	-	4-Cl		1712	3158	1691	3134	1600	-
2,3-(CH_3) ₂		1662	2915	1611	3061	1696	3218	2,3- Cl_2		1620	2956	1694	3050	1732	-
2,4-(CH_3) ₂		1655	2956	1622	3056	1701	-	2,4- Cl_2		-	-	1695	3078	-	-
2,5-(CH_3) ₂		1664	-	1600	3148	1695	-	2,5- Cl_2		1683	3357	1691	3187	1729	-
2,6-(CH_3) ₂		1647	2971	1615	3144	1695	2924	2,6- Cl_2		1681	-	1641	3144	-	-
3,4-(CH_3) ₂		1674	2925	1676	3153	1775	-	3,4- Cl_2		1675	-	1682	3225	-	-
3,5-(CH_3) ₂		1666	2921	1680	3162	1650	-	3,5- Cl_2		1690	-	1685	3268	-	-
2,4,6-(CH_3) ₃		-	-	1656	3196	-	-	2,4,6- Cl_3		-	3356	1697	3096	1707	-

Fig. 1. Line diagram for the variation of $\gamma_{C=O}$ (IR).

Fig. 2. Line diagram for the variation of $\gamma_{C=O}$ (Raman).

Fig. 3. Line diagram for the variation of γ_{N-H} (IR).

Fig. 4. Line diagram for the variation of γ_{N-H} (Raman).

phoryl chloride^{4,8}. The commercial anilines (Sisco Research Laboratories, India) were purified by either double-distillation or zone refining. Pure samples of the respective anilines (2-methylaniline, 3-methylaniline, 4-methylaniline, 2,3-dimethylaniline, 2,4-dimethylaniline, 2,5-dimethylaniline, 2,6-dimethylaniline, 3,4-dimethylaniline, 3,5-dimethylaniline, 2,4,6-trimethylaniline; 2-chloroaniline, 3-chloroaniline, 4-

chloroaniline, 2,3-dichloroaniline, 2,4-dichloroaniline, 2,5-dichloroaniline, 2,6-dichloroaniline, 3,4-dichloroaniline, 3,5-dichloroaniline, 2,4,6-trichloroaniline) were treated with mixtures of dichloroacetic acid (Aldrich) and phosphoryl chloride with constant stirring. The resulting mixtures were slowly warmed to expel HCl. Excess phosphoryl chloride was hydrolyzed by adding cold water dropwise under ice-cold conditions. HCl produced was removed by treating with

excess 2 M NaOH. The solids separated were washed thoroughly with water and dried. The substituted phenyl-dichloroacetamides were crystallized from ethanol several times. Purity of the compounds was checked by elemental analysis and by determining their melting points (Table 7). All other reagents employed were of A.R. grade.

selected for laser Raman spectral experiments. The spectra were recorded from microcrystalline samples.

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Table 7. Elemental analysis of the acetanilides studied, $X_yC_6H_{5-y}NHCOCHCl_2$

X_y	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			M.p °C
	N	C	H	
2-CH ₃	6.41 (6.42)	49.27 (49.57)	3.98 (4.16)	130
3-CH ₃	6.40 (6.42)	49.55 (49.57)	3.94 (4.16)	99
4-CH ₃	6.35 (6.42)	49.67 (49.57)	4.01 (4.16)	152
2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	6.03 (6.03)	51.75 (51.75)	4.78 (4.78)	166
2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	6.02 (6.03)	51.03 (51.75)	4.78 (4.78)	157
2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	5.90 (6.03)	49.93 (51.75)	4.87 (4.78)	150
2,6-(CH ₃) ₂	5.91 (6.03)	51.35 (51.75)	4.72 (4.78)	158
3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	5.98 (6.03)	51.55 (51.75)	4.68 (4.78)	168
3,5-(CH ₃) ₂	6.00 (6.03)	51.32 (51.75)	4.65 (4.78)	128
2,3-Cl ₂	5.11 (5.08)	34.96 (35.04)	1.67 (1.99)	136
2,4-Cl ₂	4.95 (5.08)	35.22 (35.04)	1.72 (1.99)	131
2,5-Cl ₂	4.95 (5.08)	35.14 (35.04)	1.72 (1.99)	146
2,6-Cl ₂	5.09 (5.08)	35.39 (35.04)	1.92 (1.99)	172
3,4-Cl ₂	5.03 (5.08)	35.82 (35.04)	2.11 (1.99)	142
3,5-Cl ₂	5.23 (5.08)	35.05 (35.04)	2.04 (1.99)	139
2,4,6-Cl ₃	3.58 (3.68)	25.21 (25.41)	1.07 (1.05)	187

Infrared spectra (solid state/nujol) were measured on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT-IR spectrophotometer. The resolution was set to 1 cm⁻¹ and the scanning range 400–4000 cm⁻¹. NaCl prism was used in the measurement. Raman spectra were measured on a Ramanor HG-25 spectrometer (Jobin-Yvon, France). The resolution of the spectrometer was better than 0.5 cm⁻¹. The excitation source was a 4 W argon ion laser (Coherent, U.S.A.) and 488 nm line was